

Diversity Analysis in Linseed (*Linum Usitatissimum* L.) Genotypes Based on Plant Growth and Yield Related Traits Under Salinity Stress

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted to assess the extent of genetic diversity and variability in 10 linseed genotypes grown at 4 locations of the South-Western coastal saline affected region of Bangladesh for three consecutive years based on days to germination (DG), 50% flowering (DF) and maturity (DM), plant height (PH), number of primary branch (BPP), capsule (CPP) and seed per plant (SPP), seed per capsule (SPC), 1000-seed weight (TSW) and seed yield per hectare (YLD). The data on these traits were used to estimate the genetic variability parameters, heritability and genetic advance. Analysis of variance revealed highly significant difference among ten linseed genotypes for all studied traits. Combined analysis of variance revealed highly significant main effects for all traits of ten genotypes indicating a wide range of variations among the genotype. Evaluated characters showed diverse variability, heritability and genetic advance among the genotypes. The genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) and phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) were low for DM (7.45 and 7.53) and medium for DF (10.91, 10.96) and high for the rest eight traits (GCV=60.73 to 95.68, PCV=60.91 to 95.89). Under all traits, the PCV was slightly higher than the corresponding GCV indicating high genetic influence and low environmental influence on the expression of genotypic potentiality. High values for GCV and PCV indicated high variability in genotypes. The values of heritability (H^2) varied from 36.00 to 94.00% for ten traits studied. The lowest H^2 (as percentage of mean) was found for DF and YLD, while the highest H^2 was found for BPP, followed by TSW and DG. Low genetic advance as the percentage of mean (GAM) was found for DM (7.76%), DF (8.23%) and YLD (8.23%), while high GAM was recorded for BPP (185.90%), SPC (141.17%), SPP (135.60%), DG (114.31%), PH (125.57%), CPP (119.18%) and TSW (114.31%). Based on findings of the present investigation, it may be concluded that enough genetic variability among the tested genotypes and highly significant correlation between the desirable traits with better performance are existed indicating the possibility of future genetic improvement in linseed for economic traits in salt affected soil.

Keywords: *Linseed, flax, Linum usitatissimum L., soil salinity, genetic improvement.*

Suggested citation: Kohinoor, H., Mahfuza, S.N., Sultana, N.A., Islam, M.A., & Chowdhury, A.K. (2025). Diversity Analysis in Linseed (*Linum Usitatissimum L.*) Genotypes Based on Plant Growth and Yield Related Traits Under Salinity Stress. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(6), 233-245. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(6).22

Introduction

Linseed or flax (*Linum usitatissimum L.*) belonging to the Linaceae family is an important and ancient crop in the world. Mostly, it is produced and used for its oil and fiber. The oil obtained from linseed is widely used in paint, varnish, soap and many other industrial products. Linseed oil is also suitable for cooking (Hosseinian et al. 2017). The cake added after oil extraction is an important feed source for the rapid growth of livestock (Sankari 2000). Seeds of linseed have food, nutritional and medicinal values due to the health benefits of some of their bioactive components like alpha-linolenic acid (ALA, omega-3 fatty acid), lignans and fiber (Singh et al. 2011, Goyal et al. 2014 & Kalal 2022).

Although linseed has much economic, food, nutritional and medicinal benefits, the scale of its cultivation in Bangladesh is decreasing every year due to land shortage, competition with other crops and low returns from its cultivation. The main reason for low returns from its cultivation in the country is the lack of high yielding varieties.

Linseed is a medium salinity tolerant crop (Day et al. 2017 & Dubey et al. 2020). It can be grown in the saline soils of the coastal areas of South-Western Bangladesh to reduce competition for land and to bring those saline prone lands under cultivation. Among many constraints that hinder cultivation of linseed in coastal regions, the lack of high yielding salt tolerant varieties are the most important. Therefore, development of high-yielding salt tolerant varieties is very important to encourage its cultivation and to use large areas in coastal saline soils.

Analysis of genetic divergence in available genotypes is necessary before planning appropriate breeding strategies for genetic improvement and variety development (Kumar et al. 2019). The extent of genetic diversity of existing resources play a major role in identifying parental lines and developing new varieties with desirable traits (You et al. 2019). Genetic parameters such as genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) and phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) can be used to describe divergence among genotypes. The GCV along with heritability estimates provide reliable estimates of the amount of genetic advance to be expected through phenotypic selection (Burton 1952).

The main approach of screening genotypes for salinity tolerance is growing them in the salt affected soils. The cultivation and growth of linseed in saline areas has been widely used in screening for the selection of salt tolerant varieties (Ashraf and Tufail 1995, Kaya et al. 2012 & Yasar and Yetissin 2023).

Under the above circumstances the present study was undertaken to determine the genetic variability and heritability of desired traits in 10 linseed genotypes in salinity affected fields of South-Western Bangladesh for future breeding program on the crop.

Materials and Methods

Selection of Genotypes

A total of 10 linseed genotypes were obtained from the Genetic Resource Center of Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Gazipur, Bangladesh. These were (G01) Neela, (G02) BD-10708, (G03) BD-10707, (G04) Lin-1403, (G05) Lin-2403, (G06) BD-10698, (G07) Lin-S-19, (G08) Lin-1503/2,

(G09) Lin-1203 and (G10) Lin-W-17 (Table 1). The genotype G01 is a nationally released variety which was included in the present experiment as a standard check material.

Location and Duration of Experiment

The genotypes were tested at (E1) Uttar Kalayanpur and (E2) Dokkhin Kalayanpur under Amtali upazila in Barguna district and at (E3) Diaramkhola and (E4) Nayapara under Kalapara upazila in Patuakhali district of Bangladesh. The locations of the experiment are representatives of saline soils in the South-West Coastal region under AEZ-13 of Bangladesh.

The experiment was conducted in 3 consecutive *Rabi* (winter) season (December to April) of 2020-21, 2021-22 and 2022-23. Combination a year and a location were considered as one separate environment. So, three years and four locations constituted altogether 12 test environments (Table 1).

The latitude, longitude and altitude of Amtali upzila were 22.129 °N, 90.229 °E and 1.9 m and these of Kalapara were 21.986 °N, 90.242 °E and 3.5 m, respectively. During the months of experiment (December to April) temperature, rainfall and rainy days respectively were 15.31-31.13°C, 13.47 mm and 2.03 at Amtali, and 18.3-29.5 °C, 14.36 mm and 3.34 at days Kalapara. The soil pH (0-10 cm deep), soil salinity (0-10 cm deep) respectively were 5.7-6.9 and 3.8-11.9 dS m⁻¹ at Uttar Kalayanpur, 6.0-7.1 and 9.0-15.4 dS m⁻¹ at Dokkhin Kalayanpur, 5.7-6.8 and 8.0-14.8 dS m⁻¹ at Diaramkhola, and 5.7-7.0 and 8.5-15.3 dS m⁻¹ at Narayanpur (Table 2). The weather data were the averages of three cropping seasons.

Table 1. Geographic Position, Soil Salinity, Air Temperature and Rainfall of Experimental Locations under Two Districts of Bangladesh

Location	Uttar Kalayanpur	Dokkhin Kalayanpur	Diaramkhola	Nayapara
	Under upzila Amtali & district Barguna		Under upzila Kalapara & district Patuakhali	
Latitude	22.129 °N		21.986 °N	
Longitude	90.229 °E		90.242 °E	
Altitude	1.9 m		3.5 m	
Temperature* (Min-Max)	15.4- 31.1°C		18.3-29.5 °C	
Rainfall*	13.47 mm		14.36 mm	
Rainy days	2.03 days		3.34 days	
Salinity (0-10 cm deep)	3.8-11.9 dS m ⁻¹	9.0-15.4 dS m ⁻¹	8.0-14.8 dS m ⁻¹	8.5-15.3 dSm ⁻¹

Table 2. Descriptions of Testing Environments Consisted of Three Cropping Years and Four Locations

Code	Name	Code	Name	Code	Name
E1	Uttar Kalayanpur 2020-21	E2	Uttar Kalayanpur 2021-22	E3	Uttar Kalayanpur 2022-23
E4	Dokkhin Kalayanpur 2020-21	E5	Dokkhin Kalayanpur 2021-22	E6	Dokkhin Kalayanpur 2022-23
E7	Diaramkhola 2020-21	E8	Diaramkhola 2021-22	E9	Diaramkhola 2022-23
E10	Nayapara 2020-21	E11	Nayapara 2021-22	E12	Nayapara 2022-23

Experimental Design and Layout

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. Each experimental unit was represented by a 4 m x 1 m plot planted with two rows of each genotype. Row to row distance was 40 cm and plant to plant distance was 10 cm. Space between plots was 50 cm. The standard production package was followed to have a good crop.

Data Collection

Experimental plots were visited regularly and data were collected on number of days to germination, (DG), number of days to 50% flowering (DF) and number of days for maturity (DM). At maturity stage, 20 linseed plants were randomly selected from the middle of the each unit plot and data on plant height (PHM), number of primary branches per plant (BPP), number of capsules per plant (CPP), number of seeds capsule per capsule (SPC) and number of seeds plant (SPP) were recorded. Total number of plants in a plot was harvested at fully matured stage, dried in the sun and seed were separated from the branches by manual threshing. Seeds were sun dried and 1000-seed weight and plot wise yield were recorded. The seed yield was converted to kilogram per hectare (kg ha^{-1}).

Data Analysis

Analysis of variance

Combined analysis of variance was performed for each trait according the methodology advocated by Gomez and Gomez (1983) using STAR computer software (IRRI 2014) and MS Excel.

Genetic analysis

The variability among the genotypes were estimated using mean, range, coefficient of variation, phenotypic variance (V_p) and genotypic variance (V_g). The genotypic, environmental and phenotypic variances were estimated according to Terfa and Gurmu (2020) using the following equations:

- (i) Genotypic variance (V_g)

$$V_g = \frac{MST - MSE}{r} \quad (1)$$

- (ii) Environmental variance (V_e)

$$V_e = MSE \quad (2)$$

- (iii) Phenotypic variance (V_p)

$$V_p = V_g + V_e \quad (3)$$

where, MSt = Mean squares of genotype, MSe = Mean squares of error and r = Number of replications.

The resulting components of variances were used to compute the phenotypic and genotypic coefficient of variation and genetic advances as:

- (iv) Phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV)

- (v)

$$PCV = \frac{\sqrt{V_p}}{\bar{x}} * 100 \quad (4)$$

(vi) Genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV), as suggested by Singh and Chaudhary (1985).

$$GCV = \frac{\sqrt{V_g}}{\bar{X}} * 100 \quad (5)$$

(vii) Genetic Advances (GA)

$$GA = k * \frac{V_g}{\sqrt{V_p}} \quad (6)$$

and

(vii) Genetic Advances as % of mean (GAM%) GAM% according to Allard (1960),

$$GAM\% = \frac{GA}{Mean} * 100 \quad (7)$$

where, \bar{X} = Grand mean,

V_g = (Genotypic mean square – Error mean square) ÷ number of replications,

V_p = Genotype mean square/number of replications,

i = standard selection differential (2.06) for 5% selection intensity.

Broad sense heritability (H^2) was measured as the proportion of phenotypic variance that is due to genetic differences among genotypes and was calculated according to Hanson (1963) and Nyquist (1991) as follows:

$$H^2 = \frac{V_g}{(V_g) + (V_{lyg}/ly) + (V_{lg}/l) + (V_{yg}/y) + (V_e/rly)} \quad (8)$$

where, H^2 is the broad-sense heritability, V_g is the genetic variance, V_{lyg} is the variance associated with genotype x location x year interaction, V_{lg} the variance associated with genotype x location interaction and V_{yg} is the variance associated with genotype x year interaction; while V_e is the experimental error. The terms $l, y, g,$ and r indicate the number of location, year, genotypes and replications, respectively.

The PCV and GCV were expressed in percentage of mean and classified into three classes according to the scale suggested by Sivasubramanian and Madhavamenon (1973), where Low = less than 10%, Moderate 10 to 20% and High = More than 20% values. The heritability and genetic advance were classified based on a scale advocated by Johnson et al. (1955). The GAM was categorized into three classes: Low = Less than 10%, Moderate = 10-20% and High = More than 20% values.

Results and Discussion

Analysis of Variance

The data of three years were subjected to analysis of variance following 10 x 4 x 3 factorial experiment in randomized complete block design. The results revealed highly significant ($P \leq 0.01$) main effects of genotypes (G), locations (L) and years (Y), and interaction effects of G x L, G x Y, L x Y and G x L x L (Table 3 - Appendix).

The significant interaction effects of G x L, G x Y, L x Y and G x L x L indicated that both locations and years of experiment greatly influenced expression of all traits. The results justified conducting the test in different locations and seasons. Existence of significant interaction effects may reduce gains from selection and may create some complications to identify most superior genotypes as suggested by Dyulgerova and Valcheva (2014). In such cases, breeders may attempt either to select broadly adapted genotypes with superior and stable performance across locations or to select genotypes with specific adaptation as suggested by Annichiarico (1992).

Basic Variability Parameters and Mean Performance

Mean value, range, standard deviation and coefficient of variation of all traits are presented in Table 4. Days to germination (DG), 50% flowering (DF) and maturity (DM) ranged 7.75-13.83, 56.73-62.81 and 113.83-1204.35 with a mean of 10.79, 59.77 and 117.16, respectively. Plant height (PH), number of branch (BPP), capsule per plant (CPP), seed per capsule (SPC) and seed per plant (SPP) ranged 53.83-67.15 cm, 4.15-8.68, 44.49-88.43, 4.18 to 8.95 and 153.35 to 262.95 with a mean of 60.73 cm, 6.25, 67.01, 6.55 and 204.30, respectively. Mean values of 1000-seed weight (TSW) and seed yield (YLD) per hectare were 5.86 g and 1000.10 kg ha⁻¹, while ranges for these two traits were respectively 3.67-7.73 g and 625-1345 kg ha⁻¹.

The standard deviation (SD) is a single number that summarizes the variability in a dataset. Higher value of SD indicates higher variability in the genotypes. In the current study, the lowest values of SD was recorded for 1000-seed weight (1.32 g) followed by seed capsule⁻¹ (1.58) and branch plant⁻¹ (1.80) indicating low influence of these three traits on variability of the tested linseed genotypes. The highest SD was found in case of seed yield (234.69 kg ha⁻¹) followed by numbers of seeds (37.85) and capsules (14.73) per plant, which indicated higher influence of these traits on genotype variability. The coefficient of variations (CV) ranged from 1.06 to 7.17, where the highest CV was recorded for number of seeds plant⁻¹ followed by capsules plant⁻¹ and seed capsule⁻¹ indicating their high contribution towards variability of the genotypes (Table 4). The results revealed a wide range of diversity in the experimental materials for the most of the characters studied. Significant variation for different characters was also observed by earlier workers (Payasi et al. 2000 & Ahmad et al. 2014). The wide variability for yield contributing characters in linseed was also reported by Paul et al. (2015). Variability in maize genotypes have been reported by Shah et al. (2018) based on SD and CD.

Table 4. Basic Variability Parameters for Ten Germination and Early Seedling Growth Related Parameters of Linseed under Control and Salinity Stress

Trait	Mean±SE	Minimum	Minimum	CV (%)	Std. Dev.
Days to germination (DG)	10.42±0.34	7.75	13.83	4.73	2.03
Days to 50% flowering (DF)	51.95±0.34	56.73	62.81	1.06	2.03
Days to maturity (DM)	116.5±0.36	113.80	120.40	1.11	2.17
Plant height (cm) (PH)	6.48±0.30	4.15	8.68	6.45	1.80
Branch per plant (BPP)	61.25±0.82	53.83	67.15	2.26	4.94
Capsule per plant (CPP)	7.42±2.45	44.49	88.43	6.93	14.73
Seed per capsule (SPC)	6.55±0.26	4.18	8.95	6.55	1.58

Seed per plant (SPP)	210.1±6.31	153.40	263.00	7.17	37.85
1000-Seed weight (g) (TSW)	116.5±0.36	3.67	7.73	5.27	1.32
Days to germination (DG)	1000.0±39.1	625.00	1345.00	4.57	234.69

Estimation of Variance

Genetic improvement is an important tool to enhance the productivity of a crop. Genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV), phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) and environmental coefficient of variation are useful to explain and understand the variations among genotypes. High variability in a population enables the plant breeders to select genotypes for varietal development with desirable traits like high yield (Singh et al. 2007) and salt tolerance. Sivasubramanian and Madhavamenon (1973) suggested to classify the PCV and GCV based on their percentage of mean where Low= $<10\%$, Moderate= 10 to 20% and High= $>20\%$.

Estimated genotypic variance (V_g), phenotypic variance (V_p), GCV, PCV, broad sense heritability (H^2) and genetic advance (GA) as a percentage of mean for all studied traits are presented in Table 5 and Figure 1. The V_g and V_p were the highest for seed yield ha^{-1} ($V_g=661924.15$, $V_p=664014.23$) followed by number of seeds per plant ($V_g=25776.40$, $V_p=26003.36$), capsule per plant ($V_g=2710.08$, $V_p=2736.50$) and plant height ($V_g=2699.72$, $V_p=3147.82$). The GCV and PCV as percentage of mean were 7.45% and 7.53% for days to maturity (low), and 10.91 and 10.96 for days to 50% flowering (medium) respectively. The GCV ranged 60.73 to 95.68% and PCV ranged 60.91 to 95.89% for other 8 traits. Under all traits, the PCV was slightly higher than the corresponding GCV (Table 4). The low differences between PCV and GCV for various traits indicated high genetic influence and low environmental influence on the expression of genotypic potentiality. High values for GCV and PCV indicated existence of high variability among genotypes for all traits.

In the present investigation, high GCV and PCV values were found for seed yield per plant and per hectare, number of branch per plant, number of capsules per plant and 1000-seed weight indicating high variability in these traits (Table 4). Under all traits, the PCV was slightly higher than the corresponding GCV. The low differences between PCV and GCV for various traits indicated high genetic influence on the expression of genotypic potentiality. The results suggest that there are sufficient scopes for improvement of linseed variety through selection; and the traits under study were less influenced by environment. Similar results on linseed were also reported by Kumar et al. (2015), Paul et al. (2017) and Terfa and Gurmu (2020).

Estimated Heritability in Broad-Sense

Heritability in broad-sense is an important indicator of transferring traits from parents to its progenies. The estimates of heritability help the plant breeder in selection of genotypes from diverse genetic populations. High degree of heritability is desirable because of its effectiveness for selection for a particular trait. Kumar et al. (2016) reported that heritability is an important index of transmission of characters from parents to its progeny. Johnson et al. (1955) advocated a scale to classify heritability into 3 categories as Low= $<10\%$, Moderate= 10 - 20% and High= $>20\%$ values.

In the current study, most of the traits expressed high estimates of broad sense heritability. The heritability values varied from 36.00 to 94.00% among ten traits studied, which were categorized as high. The lowest H^2 was found for days to 50% flowering and seed yield per hectare, while the highest H^2 was found for primary branch per plant, followed by 1000-seed weight followed by days to germination (91.00%) (Table 4 and Fig. 1).

Estimate of Expected Genetic Advance

The genetic advance (GA) is a very useful indicator, which helps to select desirable genotype effectively and efficiently based on genetic variability in available populations (Terfa and Gurmu 2020). The genetic

advance is expressed as a percentage of mean (GAM) and categorized into three classes base on its estimated values as advocated by Johnson et al. (1955), where Low = Less than 10%, Moderate = 10-20% and High = More than 20% values.

In the present study, genetic advance as percentage of mean was 7.76, 8.23 and 8.23% for days to maturity, days to 50% flowering and seed yield per hectare, respectively, which were classified as low. On the other hand, the maximum genetic advance as percentage of mean was recorded for branch per plant (185.900%) followed by seed per capsule (141.17%) and seed per plant (135.60%). The genetic parameter was 114.31, 125.57, 119.18 and 114.31% for days to germination, plant height, capsule per plant and 1000-seed weight. The genetic parameters for other 7 traits were classified as high (Table 5 and Fig. 1).

Table 5. Genetic Variability Parameters of 10 Traits of 10 Linseed Genotypes Grown at 4 Locations over 3 Consecutive *Rabi* Seasons

Trait	Vg	Vp	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	ECV	H ² %	GA	GAM (%)
Days to germination	40.04	40.28	60.73	60.91	2.14	91.00	11.91	114.31
Days to 50% flowering	45.63	46.06	10.91	10.96	0.06	36.00	5.09	8.23
Days to maturity	75.32	76.98	7.45	7.53	0.26	48.00	8.69	7.46
Plant height (cm)	2699.72	3147.82	84.90	91.68	3.41	66.00	76.85	125.57
Branch per plant	38.44	38.61	95.68	95.89	1.08	94.00	12.05	185.90
Capsule per plant	2710.08	2736.53	75.12	75.49	55.73	77.00	82.59	119.18
Seed per capsule	26.00	26.17	77.85	78.11	0.95	88.00	9.25	141.17
Seed per plant	25776.40	26003.36	76.41	76.75	93.78	86.00	284.92	135.60
1000-Seed weight (g)	20.08	20.17	77.66	77.84	1.87	91.00	11.91	114.31
Seed yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	661924.2	664014.20	81.36	81.49	115.47	36.00	5.09	8.23

Note: SE=Standard error, SD=Standard deviation, CV= Coefficient of variation, Vg = Genotypic variance, Vp=Phenotypic variance, GCV= Genotypic coefficient of variability, PCV=Phenotypic coefficient of variability, H² = Heritability (broad-sense), GA= Genetic advance, GAM%= GA as % of mean

Figure 1. Bar Chart Depicting Estimates of Genotypes Coefficient of Variation (GCV), Phenotypic Coefficient of Variation (PCV), Broad-Sense Heritability (H²) and Genetic Advance as Percent Mean (GAM) for 12 Traits of Ten Linseed Genotypes

Significant genetic diversity in the breeding stocks is a prerequisite as it not only provides a basis for selection but it also provides some important information regarding the selection of different parents for hybridization programs (Singh et al. 2016 & Upadhyay et al. 2019). High PCV and GCV indicate a substantial degree of genetic diversity, while features characterized by low PCV and GCV values signify a lower degree of diversity (Terfa and Gurmu 2020 & Yadav et al. 2024). In the current study, the ANOVA revealed highly significant ($P \leq 0.0000$) mean sum of square of genotypes for all traits indicating the existence of a high diversity among linseed genotypes tested suggesting opportunities for crop improvement through selection. Previously, similar magnitude of variability for days to 50% flowering and maturity, plant height, number of branches per plant, number of capsule per plant, number of seeds per capsule, and seed yield of linseed have been reported by other investigators (Kumar et al. 2019, Patial et al. 2019, Terfa and Gurmu 2020, Patel et al. 2023, Yadav et al. 2024). Patel et al. (2023) reported a wide range of genetic variability of economically related traits which are in confirmation with the results of the present study. Traits with moderate or high heritability indicate the dominance of genetic contributions for these traits, whereas traits with low genetic progress (% of mean) are dominated by non-additive genetic action. These environmental effects may be due to differences in soil fertility and other unpredictable factors (Reddy et al. 2012). Different researchers believe that these traits should be controlled rather than selected for improving performance (Vashistha et al. 2013 Yadav et al. 2024). The current study shows that genetic advance expressed as percentage of mean (GAM%) is more consistent with heritability than heritability alone in predicting the results when selecting genotypes of individual traits. The heritability potential with average percentage of genetic success provides the potential for improvement through selection (Singh et al. 2016).

Conclusion

Analysis of phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) and genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV), heritability (H^2) and genetic advance (GA) are widely used tools to assess genetic diversity in a population of crop species. Traits with high PCV and GCV values indicate high variability, while traits with low PCV and GCV values indicate low genetic variability. The higher the difference, the better the selection can be made to improve the crop. The lowest GCV and highest PCV indicate the quality of the environment because PCV is higher than GCV. Moderate to low variance indicates the need for improvement in the outcome. The broad-sense heritability (H^2) for almost all traits was high to very high (36.00 to 94.00%) in the current study. The lowest (H^2) was found for days to 50% flowering and seed yield per hectare, while the highest H^2 was found for primary branch per plant, followed by 1000-seed weight followed by days to germination (91.00%). The genetic advance as percentage of mean (GAM) was low for days to maturity, 50% flowering, and seed yield, while it was high for branch per plant, seed per capsule, seed per plant, days to maturity, plant height, capsule per plant and 1000-seed weight. The findings of the present investigation revealed that enough genetic variability among the tested genotypes and highly significant correlation between the desirable traits with better performance are existed indicating the possibility of future genetic improvement using the tested genotypes in linseed for economic traits especially in salt affected soil.

Acknowledgement

The study was undertaken with the financial support of the Krishi Gabeshona Foundation (KGF), Bangladesh Agricultural Research Council, Dhaka, Bangladesh and Water Security Program, CSIRO, Black Mountain Laboratories, GPO Box 1700, Canberra ACT 2601, Australia. The authors would like to express their thanks to Bangladesh Agriculture Research Institute, Gazipur, Bangladesh providing all research facilities and laboratory services to carry out this research.

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Appendix

Table 3. Combined Analysis of Variance (10 x 4 x 3 Factorial in RCBD) for Ten Traits of 10 Linseed Genotypes across 12 Environments (4 Locations over 3 Consecutive Seasons)

Source of variation	df	Days to Germination	Days to flowering	Days to Maturity	Plant height (cm)	Branch per plant	Capsule per plant	Seed per plant	Seed per plant	1000-Seed wt. (g)	Seed Yield (kg/ha)
Replication	8	0.223 ^{ns}	0.040 ^{ns}	0.308 ^{ns}	2.086 ^{ns}	0.070 ^{ns}	38.62 ^{**}	0.062 ^{ns}	197.04 ^{ns}	0.108 ^{ns}	1154.73 ^{ns}
Genotype (G)	9	120.361 ^{**}	137.326 ^{**}	227.611 ^{**}	8547.27 ^{**}	115.49 ^{**}	8156.69 ^{**}	78.178 ^{**}	77556.17 ^{**}	60.327 ^{**}	1987862.52 ^{**}
Year (Y)	2	12.228 ^{**}	555.418 ^{**}	288.773 ^{**}	783.105 ^{**}	5.768 ^{**}	1102.30 ^{**}	7.135 ^{**}	3200.35 ^{**}	6.214 ^{**}	13752.51 ^{**}
Location (L)	3	9.778 ^{**}	280.599 ^{**}	216.393 ^{**}	3863.481 ^{**}	5.61 ^{**}	18354.31 ^{**}	21.599 ^{**}	55365.30 ^{**}	15.697 ^{**}	76497.65 ^{**}
L x G	27	2.082 ^{**}	5.280 ^{**}	15.712 ^{**}	2285.84 ^{**}	2.25 ^{**}	136.86 ^{**}	2.021 ^{**}	2631.13 ^{**}	1.239 ^{**}	22282.46 ^{**}
L x Y	6	1.483 ^{**}	1.999 ^{**}	5.322 ^{**}	7831.00 ^{**}	2.62 ^{**}	210.25 ^{**}	1.223 ^{**}	3035.77 ^{**}	0.577 ^{**}	50227.17 ^{**}
G x Y	18	9.594 ^{**}	234.020 ^{**}	230.344 ^{**}	1304.65 ^{**}	2.20 ^{**}	2335.60 ^{**}	9.048 ^{**}	10328.60 ^{**}	14.205 ^{**}	17678.14 ^{**}
L x G x Y	54	2.229 ^{**}	3.199 ^{**}	7.0030 ^{**}	4100.46 ^{**}	13.283 ^{**}	147.77 ^{**}	1.300 ^{**}	2036.084 ^{**}	0.975 ^{**}	19542.79 ^{**}
Residual	232	0.240	0.430	1.663	448.101	0.175	26.45	0.172	226.956	0.093	2090.08
Total	359										

Note: df = degrees of freedom, ^{ns}Not significant at 0.05% probability level, ^{**}Significant at 0.01% probability level.

